

Thrips affected by steam distillates of resistant varieties and wild rices

R. Velusamy, M. Ganesh Kumar, and Y. S. Johnson Thangaraj Edward, Agricultural Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India; and B. Thayumanavan and S. Sadasivam, Biochemistry Department, TNAU

Extracts of steam distillates of varieties Ptb21, Rathu Heenati, and Swarnalata and wild rices *Oryza officinalis* (Acc. 101114) and *O. latifolia* (Acc. 100963) were bioassayed against greenhouse-reared *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall).

Leaves of 30-d-old plants grown in an insectproof screenhouse were harvested and ground with an electric grinder. Distillation and extraction were done following the Saxena and Skech method developed at IRRI.

Susceptible TN1 plants were grown in 16-cm-diam pots. Single tillers of 30-d-old plants were sprayed with 1 ml of acetone-water solution containing extract at the rate of 2,000 ppm. Controls were treated with acetone or nothing.

To determine the effect of the extracts on oviposition behavior of thrips, each plant was infested with five gravid females and then covered with a mylar cage. Eggs were counted 3 d after their release.

To determine toxicity, ten 1st-instar larvae were placed on each seedling after the acetone had evaporated; the seedling was then covered with a mylar cage. Larval mortality was recorded after 24 h. Each treatment was replicated five times and arranged in a randomized complete block design.

All of the extracts adversely affected the ovipositional behavior of *S. biformis* (see table). The wild rice extracts were more effective than those of the resistant varieties.

All of the extracts were toxic to some degree to 1st-instar thrips. The wild rice extracts were most toxic (see table). ■

Effect of steam distillate extracts of resistant varieties and wild rices on *S. biformis* ovipositional behavior and larval mortality.^a

Treatment	Eggs laid (no.)	Larval mortality (%)
Control	25 a ± 1.30	2 c ± 0.63
Control (acetone)	22 a ± 1.30	4 c ± 0.63
Ptb21	9 cd ± 0.71	40 b ± 3.16
Rathu Heenati	11 bc ± 0.71	44 b ± 2.45
Swarnalata	13 b ± 1.14	36 b ± 4.00
<i>O. officinalis</i>	4 e ± 0.71	82 a ± 3.74
<i>O. latifolia</i>	7 de ± 0.71	76 a ± 5.10
SEM	1.24	3.35

^a Mean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Sampling spiders during the rice fallow period

G. S. Arida and K. L. Heong, IRRI

Spiders commonly found on growing rice either migrate to nonrice environments after harvest or remain within the harvested field, residing in soil crevices or on bunds during the fallow period. Methods to sample arthropod populations from growing rice are not adequate for sampling crevices during the fallow period.

We compared different sampling techniques in a ricefield in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 3 wk after harvest. The field was dry with soil crevices about 40 cm deep. A square (1 × 1 × 0.3 m) metal frame (gauge #12) was placed randomly in the field and hammered 5 cm below ground level. A sticky material (Tanglefoot) was applied in a 5-cm-wide strip on both the outside and inside of the frame above ground level to prevent spiders from moving in and out of the sampling area. The experiment was replicated four times.

Spiders in the enclosed area were sampled by simple observation, pouring water inside the frame, and digging into the crevices. With the first technique, spiders were observed for some time and then caught as they emerged from crevices. Individuals trapped in the metal frames were also collected. The other techniques involved forcing the arthropods out: in the second, about 300 liters

Spiders (no.)

Species and number of spiders collected per m² from soil crevices 3 wk after rice harvest. Nueva Ecija, Philippines. 1993 dry season.

of water per frame were poured into the crevices; in the third, the crevices were opened with a metal bar. For all methods, spiders leaving the crevices were either collected by hand or were caught in the sticky material and then collected. The frames were left overnight and catches on the inside were later gathered.

Results show that spiders inhabited field crevices even at 3 wk after harvest (see figure). Pouring water inside a frame appears to be an effective sampling method and is especially good for catching jumping spiders, such as *Pardosa* sp. ■